

Retailing Ethics Of Selected Online Stores As Perceived By The Consumers In Doha, State Of Qatar

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Abstract: Introduction: *Retailing ethics* is critical in shaping consumer trust and loyalty, especially in online commerce, where ethical concerns such as *Privacy*, *Security*, and deceptive practices impact consumer behavior. The objective of this study was to assess the retailing ethics of selected online stores in Doha, State of Qatar, as perceived by consumers based on the six ethical dimensions: *Privacy*, *Security*, *Reliability*, *Non-deception*, *Service Recovery*, and *Shared Value*. **Methodology:** A descriptive-comparative research design was employed, utilizing a validated and reliable survey instrument adapted from the research paper, 'Development and Validation of an Instrument to Measure Online Retailing Ethics: Consumers' Perspective' by Agag et al. Data was collected through online and physical surveys with 117 respondents. The instrument underwent content validation and reliability testing using Lawshe's content validity ratio and Cronbach's Alpha, where the research was validated and found reliable. Statistical analysis, including T-test, was conducted to determine significant distinctions in consumer perception based on age and sex. **Results:** The results indicated that consumers generally perceived online retailers as ethical, though concerns persisted regarding deceptive marketing and service recovery. Younger consumers valued *Security*, *Reliability*, and *Service Recovery* more positively than older consumers, suggesting differences in trust levels across age groups. However, perceptions did not significantly vary according to sex, indicating a consistent ethical outlook between male and female consumers. **Discussion:** The study underscored the significance of ethical standards in online retail, stressing the importance of openness, honest marketing, and practical strategies for addressing service issues. The results offered valuable guidance for online retailers aiming to strengthen consumer confidence and improve overall satisfaction. **Conclusion:** To foster consumer trust and long-term loyalty, online retailers must prioritize ethical business practices, particularly in addressing deceptive marketing. Enhancing transparency, improving communication, and reinforcing ethical policies will be crucial in strengthening consumer confidence. These improvements can help online businesses build a stronger reputation and ensure sustainable growth in the competitive e-commerce industry.

Keywords: Consumer Perception; E-commerce; Online Retailing Ethics; Consumer Trust; Consumer Loyalty; Ethical Dimensions; Consumer Perception; Online Retailers; Ethical Practices; Transparency; Deceptive Marketing; Service Quality; Qatar; Doha; Demographic Differences; Trust Factors; Ethics

Introduction

In the era of information-communication technology and the rapid Development of electronic commerce, consumers can purchase almost anything, anywhere, and at any time (Yang & Yan, 2020). In the 21st century the advent of technology and its features has revolutionized openness, participation, and facilitation of consumer brand engagement and its impacts on customer practices (Naeem & Okafor, 2019). Instances of perceived unethical behavior by online retailers, such as misleading advertising or price gouging, can potentially erode consumer trust and loyalty, thereby impacting the reputation and profitability of these businesses (Vorderer et al., 2016). It is essential to determine ethical reflections and guidelines for customer experience design and management (Velasco et al., 2024). The ethical dimension of business operations, especially within online retailing, has garnered significant attention in recent years. With consumers increasingly turning to digital platforms for their shopping needs, the importance of ethical conduct by online retailers cannot be overstated (Cheung & To, 2016).

This study aims to explore consumer perceptions of ethics in terms of online retailing specifically on selected online stores, shedding light on its significance for the sustainability and success of online businesses. Nowadays, plenty of internet users engage in online shopping. Ethical consumption in online retailing is becoming increasingly popular, with research indicating that consumers consider ethical considerations when making purchasing decisions (Kim, 2019). The rapid expansion of online retailing has created numerous opportunities for both businesses and consumers for people worldwide conducting online transactions (Yuniarti et al., 2022). However, this growth also brings forth ethical challenges that cannot be overlooked. Studies have indicated that the internet environment is susceptible to unethical behavior, with privacy breaches and security concerns prevailing (Vederhus & Nath, 2022; Liu & Ling, 2017; Akter, 2020; Dang & Pham, 2018). Despite recognizing these ethical concerns, empirical research addressing online retailing ethics from the consumers' perspective remains limited.

Despite customer's rising expectations, the ethical practices of e-retailers have received limited scrutiny in marketing literature. Previous research has underscored the paramount importance of trust as a key success factor in ecommerce (Al-Azzawi et al., 2021). Additionally, studies have highlighted the significance of commitment in fostering and sustaining positive relationships between consumers and retailers or vendors (Adjei et al., 2017). It is important to note that most studies on Consumers' Perceptions of Retailers' Ethics (CPEOR) have been conducted in developed nations (Elbeltagi & Agag, 2016), where consumer demographics, purchasing patterns, and legal structures differ greatly from those in developing nations. Consequently, a critical gap exists in understanding how consumers perceive and navigate ethical considerations within online retailing (Agag et al., 2016).

All businesses operating offline or online, including retail, must uphold ethical standards. Ethics, business ethics, and online retailer ethics generally pertain to determining the rightness or wrongness of actions. Ethical dilemmas often arise due to varying circumstances and social and cultural influences (Gupta et al., 2022). As ethical issues in online business arise with the steady growth of e-transactions, online retailers are requested to demonstrate their integrity, honesty, and sincerity and deal with customers through fair, secure, confidential, and reliable websites (Agag et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2019). Online platforms have become breeding grounds for unethical behavior, with some retailers engaging in practices such as undisclosed tracking, fraudulent activities, and misinformation (Bhattacharya et al., 2024). These actions erode consumer trust and satisfaction, leading to negative perceptions of online retailing ethics. Several factors have been identified as influencing consumer behavior in online retailing in Qatar (Alkailani et al., 2021).

The perceived risk negatively influences the customer's intentions toward online shopping, while trust and perceived technology are positively related to online shopping intentions (Ali & Top, 2021). Furthermore, cultural and ethical ideology were identified as important factors influencing consumers' perceptions of the ethics of online retailers and their loyalty (Hassan & Wood, 2020). Researchers have begun to delve into consumer perception regarding online retailing ethics, recognizing the importance of ethical conduct in fostering positive consumer relations. Various factors influence consumers' perspectives in understanding ethical considerations guiding their choices. The factors that determined the structure of e-retailing ethics were *Privacy, Security, Reliability, Non-deception, Service Recovery, and Shared Value* (Agag et al., 2016).

These online retail ethics and perceived risks are currently the most difficult challenges for consumers contemplating purchasing online (Fihartini et al., 2022). However, research on consumer perceptions in Doha, Qatar remains limited. Concerns about consumer trust in e-commerce and the importance of business ethics

have been encountered with e-commerce platforms (Musa et al., 2022). A study conducted in Thailand suggests that business ethics are a crucial factor driving a company's success and profits and that business ethics play an important role in the present era (Sukhawatthanakun, 2022). The popularity of online shopping has increased significantly in recent years due to its convenience, ease of use, efficiency, and ability to save time, money, and effort. This trend has especially caught the attention of today's students. (Chelvaryan et al., 2021)

As physical shopping becomes more challenging due to factors like time constraints, traffic congestion, and crowded spaces, more consumers are turning to online alternatives. From a consumer's perspective, online shopping offers numerous advantages over traditional methods—particularly in terms of cost, time, and convenience (Chelvaryan et al., 2021). These perceived benefits play a crucial role in shaping consumer behavior towards online purchasing (Chelvaryan et al., 2021). However, such investigations are notably absent in Doha, Qatar. Therefore, conducting research in regions like Doha could provide valuable insights into these critical issues and their implications within diverse cultural contexts. Examining the ethical conduct of online retailers, this research delves into how consumers perceive practices in the e-commerce space.

Ethical behavior among decision-makers is crucial in molding a successful business (Bulog & Grancic, 2017). It influences the public's perception of a particular brand, which is key in upholding consumer trust and loyalty (Cerchia & Piccolo, 2019). This is significant as it helps business owners establish marketing ethics in various sectors to prevent future problems (Sukhawatthanakun, 2022). By conducting this study, the researchers determined the impact of ethics on consumers' perspectives, providing valuable insights into how consumers perceive online retail ethics. Despite extensive research on online retailing ethics in developed countries, there is a noticeable lack of studies examining consumer perceptions in Doha, Qatar. Qatar's unique cultural, economic, and regulatory landscape presents distinct consumer expectations and ethical concerns that have not been thoroughly explored. To ensure consistency and adhere to ethical standards, only Grade 12 students aged 18 and above were selected as respondents. This age group is considered legally an adult and can provide informed consent, eliminating ethical concerns related to involving minors. By focusing on this age range, the study aims to gather insights from individuals who are more likely to have developed mature perspectives in online shopping. Thus ensuring that the data reflects the views of a more experienced and responsible demographic.

This study fills the gap by investigating how Doha consumers perceive the necessary ethical dimensions of *Security*, *Privacy*, *Reliability*, *Non-deception*, *Service Recovery*, and *Shared Value* in online retailing. In addition, although earlier studies have emphasized trust, transparency, and security in e-commerce, little research has been done on how demographic variables like age and gender affect these perceptions. This study sheds light on variations in ethical priorities among these groups, offering important insights that can assist online retailers in improving their ethical practices and strengthening consumer trust in Qatar's developing digital marketplace.

To further explore the influence of age on consumers' perceptions in online retailing ethics, this study targeted respondents aged 18 and above. One study found young consumers tend to exhibit a hedonic online shopping style, favoring high-quality products and seeking entertainment throughout the shopping experience. They are often impulsive buyers, drawn to novelty and brand-name items. While they may struggle with choosing between online stores and products, they demonstrate strong loyalty to particular brands and retailers (Helmi et al., 2023). Similarly, a study by Mokhtar et al. (2020) investigated young adults in Malaysia found that convenience, customer satisfaction, and price level positively influence their online shopping behavior, whereas perceived risk negatively affects it. These findings reinforce the idea that young adults value ease and satisfaction in their shopping experience. Another study found that Millennials (29-44 years old) emphasize trust, detailed product research, and alignment with sustainability values (Syamsudin et al., 2025). By having age as one of the demographics, this study aims to contribute to the knowledge on retailing ethics, and help retailers better meet the expectations of these age groups.

Theoretical framework

Figure 1: Based on Gomaa Agag, Ahmed A. El-Masry, Nawaf Alharbi, and Ahmed's "Modelling BPSE as a Reflective Second-Order".

This research delves into evaluating online retailing ethics as consumers perceive it in Doha, Qatar. It utilizes the six dimensions identified in the study by Agag et al. (2016) on measuring online retailing ethics. These dimensions include **Privacy**, which is crucial for ensuring that respondents feel their personal information is protected; **Security**, which addresses safeguards against unauthorized access and cyberthreats; and **Reliability**, reflecting the consistency and trustworthiness of services provided by online retailers. The dimensions of **Non-deception** ensures that marketing practices are transparent and not misleading, fostering an honest relationship with the consumers. Furthermore, **Service Recovery** examines how online retailers respond to customer complaints and effectively address service failure, which is vital for maintaining trust. Lastly, **Shared Value** emphasizes the alignment between a retailer's business practices and the ethical values appreciated by consumers, enhancing engagement and loyalty. By investigating these dimensions, the study aims to provide valuable insight into consumer expectations and concerns in the online retail market.

Privacy

In online retailing, ethics is significant as it impacts consumer trust, loyalty, and overall satisfaction. Privacy concerns have been found to be one of the most important factors in e-commerce adoption (Mohammed & Tejay, 2017). Maintaining data privacy in retail is crucial for negotiating tensions and guiding future research (Ogonji et al., 2020). Privacy considerations are crucial, as content moderation involves processing large amounts of personal data, necessitating safeguards to protect user information in online retailing (Ahmed & Khan, 2024). Additionally, Data privacy concerns significantly influence consumer trust in digital marketing, with transparency in data practices and regulatory compliance identified as critical factors in fostering trust (Chandreskhar et al., 2024)

Security

Security is a cornerstone of online retailing, protecting against unauthorized access, data breaches, and cyber threats. These security concerns pose significant hurdles to E-commerce growth, calling for a joint effort to speak about and build consumer trust (Imtiaz et al., 2020). Likewise, it highlights the important role of perceived Security in consumer behavior and influencing purchase decisions, focusing on the need for strong security measures in online transactions (Albert et al., 2019). Ensuring secure e-commerce applications has been found to play an important role in increasing the customer base (Saeed, 2023). Prioritizing Security protects sensitive information and fosters trust, satisfaction, and loyalty among consumers, ultimately contributing to the sustainability of e-commerce platforms. As referred to in this study by (Imtiaz et al., 2016), trust and customer satisfaction play a vital role. They can be achieved if there is Security and Privacy, highlighting their importance. Both have a positive impact on satisfaction in online shopping.

Reliability

Reliability pertains to the steadiness or constancy of a measurement (Segal & Coolidge., 2018). As perceived Reliability encourages customers to submit their online reviews on a social platform, Ventre and Kolbe (2020) further bolster the case by pointing out that this opinion favorably affects the level of trust that other buyers have in their purchase decision (Saoula et al., 2023). Reliability in delivering products or services creates trust based on the fulfillment of terms and conditions of purchase (Alkhateeb, 2020). A strong brand image, characterized by high Reliability, strengthens consumer trust, leading to increased brand preference, greater customer loyalty, and lower market competition (Ratnawati & Lestari., 2018). Customers engage with a company's website when they perceive it as a dependable platform for finding and evaluating products and submitting and reading reviews (Lăzăroiu et al., 2020). Customers who find a website easy to use, dependable, and creatively designed will likely trust the e-service provider more (Tran et al., 2019).

Non-deception

Most studies define non-deception as the degree of consumer belief that online retailers do not use manipulative practices to persuade them to purchase their products (Bhattacharya et al., 2021; Cheung & To, 2020; Elbeltagi & Agag, 2016). Marketing professionals seek to attract customers' attention by setting up campaigns or advertisements that contain attention-grabbing details or even using rare and attractive packaging for the product presented in a distinctive way (Sadiqe & Lina, 2024). Deception has long been condemned as unethical and harmful to consumers. As being misled, consumers may respond negatively to the market and marketers themselves (Viridi, 2020). Furthermore, some organizations have shifted towards the use of unethical marketing practices to increase their profit by deceiving consumers by giving them false information about products, services, promotions, prices, or distributions; this is reflected in consumer purchase decisions towards the product or services (Gshayyish, 2023). Although perceptions of non-deceptive tactics are crucial in explaining e-retailing ethics, consumers may prioritize aspects more relevant to the online environment, such as Security, Privacy, and fulfillment, in forming satisfaction and trust (Agag et al., 2016). Previous research has shown that online retailers' deceptive practices negatively impact consumer satisfaction and trust (Elbeltagi & Agag, 2016).

Service Recovery

Service Recovery is known as the effort to resolve a problem caused by service failure and restore customer satisfaction (Jung & Seock, 2017). It is one of the critical success factors that can be used to shape and measure customer satisfaction and delight (Alzoubi et al., 2019). Improper service recovery could enhance customer dissatisfaction (Chih-Hung et al., 2019). Determining the relative effects of different types of service recovery will provide strategic help for marketers seeking to find more effective and cost-efficient recovery types for their target consumers in the online market (Jung & Seock, 2017).

Shared Value

Shared value refers to the operating policies and practices that help improve the company's competitiveness while maintaining their positive impact on the economic and social conditions of the communities where they are operating. Shared value creation by coordinating business activities and social concerns brings opportunities for sustainable development (Yang & Yan, 2020). Shared values between businesses and consumers play a crucial role in fostering ethical perceptions, leading to increased trust and loyalty towards online retailers (Nadeem et al., 2021). When companies integrate sustainability initiatives that reflect consumer expectations, they strengthen their reputation and foster deeper customer engagement. Aligning business practices with shared ethical values enhances consumer trust, leading to long-term loyalty. This connection between corporate responsibility and consumer perception plays a vital role in shaping a company's competitive advantage in the online retail industry (He & Wang, 2024). Additionally, when businesses and consumers share the same ethical values, it helps create a positive work environment and strengthens a company's commitment to social responsibility. This alignment encourages businesses to act more responsibly, which improves their reputation. As a result, consumers are more likely to trust and support these companies (Khan et al., 2024).

Research Questions

The objective of this study was to determine consumers' perceptions on online retailing ethics. Specifically, this research aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the consumers in terms of age and sex?
2. What is the extent of online retailer ethics in terms of *privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value* when grouped according to:
 - 2.1 age in privacy
 - 2.2 age in security
 - 2.3 age in reliability
 - 2.4 age in non-deception
 - 2.5 age in service recovery
 - 2.6 age in shared value
 - 2.7 age when taken collectively
 - 2.8 sex in privacy
 - 2.9 sex in security
 - 2.10 sex in reliability
 - 2.11 sex in non-deception
 - 2.12 sex in service recovery
 - 2.13 sex in shared value
 - 2.14 sex when taken collectively
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of online retailers ethics in terms of *privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value* when grouped according to age and sex?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the extent of online retailers ethics in terms of *Privacy, Security, Reliability, Non-deception, Service Recovery, and Shared Value* when grouped according to age and sex.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers utilized the descriptive comparative research design. Descriptive research gathers information through observation and characterizes phenomena utilizing surveys, questionnaires, rubrics, interviews, or rankings (Deckert et al., 2023). Furthermore, as outlined by Siedlecki (2020), qualitative research focuses on characterizing phenomena without altering variables, while quantitative research involves gathering numerical data to identify trends, formulate hypotheses, and examine causality. However, this type of research design cannot conclusively determine why.

Respondents

The given sampling of this research included one hundred forty-seven respondents. Thirty of these were utilized for pilot testing to check the reliability and clarity of the questionnaire, while the remaining 117 were included in the primary data analysis. The sample size was determined using the Raosoft online sample size calculator, applying a 93% confidence level, a 7% margin of error, and a 50% response distribution. These parameters were selected to ensure the sample size would be statistically reliable while still manageable for a student research project.

Profile	n	%
Age		
Younger [18-37]	53	45.3%
Older [38+]	64	54.7%
Total	117	100%
Sex		
Male	40	34.2%
Female	77	65.8%
Total	117	100%

The population of this study included consumers living in Doha, State of Qatar, who actively purchase from popular online stores. These respondents were targeted because they have firsthand experience with online retail platforms and are capable of evaluating the ethical practices of these stores based on actual shopping behavior. The sampling method used was convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling technique, meaning participants were selected based on their accessibility, availability, and willingness to participate. The age bracket that defines the transition between young adulthood and old adulthood was based on the general average and consistency of ages throughout the population sample. This is further supported by the study adopted from Tanu et al. (2019), where ANOVA was used based on customers' demographic information such as age, outlining the average age for young adults as 37. This is further solidified by the study of Ntumi (2021), who also applied ANOVA to measure variables across distinct groups, including age, to make inferences about population means. The researchers distributed the survey through both digital platforms (such as social media and email) and physical copies in public areas like malls and schools where potential online consumers were likely to be found. This method allowed efficient data collection within a limited timeframe and available resources. All respondents gave informed consent, and their identities were kept anonymous throughout the study to maintain ethical standards.

Research Instrument

This study utilized the instrument from 'Development and Validation of an Instrument to Measure Online Retailing Ethics: Consumers' Perspective' by Agag et al. (2016) as the primary data-gathering tool. This instrument was used to understand how consumers perceive and value ethical conduct in online retailing. The questionnaire was composed of a total of 21 items, with six specific subscales tackling the perceptions of the customers in online retail ethics with *Privacy* (3 items), *Security* (3 items), *Reliability* (4 items), *Non-deception* (4 items), *Service Recovery* (4 items), and *Shared Value* (3 items). All questions can be answered using a four-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" (1) to "strongly agree" (4), with the negatively-worded questions. Reverse scoring was used for the variable "Non-Deception" because of their negative indicators; the following scales were used:

Mean Range	Description in the Instrument	Verbal Interpretation
3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Ethical
2.51 – 3.25	Agree	Ethical
1.76 – 2.50	Disagree	Slightly Ethical
1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree	Not Ethical at All

Validity and Reliability

To ensure the validity and Reliability of the instrument, it underwent a content validity ratio assessment by Lawshe, including five validators. They evaluated the instrument items as either essential, helpful but not essential, or not essential. Items with a critical value of 0.750 or higher were retained in the instrument. The result of the content validity index was 0.99; all items were retained except dimension 4, "non-deception," which was changed into its reverse form for the study. The standardized instrument's data then underwent reliability testing using Cronbach's alpha to assess the internal consistency of the pilot-tested data. This process involved thirty (30) respondents. The alpha results were 0.85, which was interpreted as reliable.

Data Collection Procedure

To gather data addressing the study's objectives, the process was structured into three phases. First, potential participants were chosen from active users of popular online shopping platforms in Doha, Qatar—such as Temu, Shein, Facebook Marketplace, and eBay—to make sure they were familiar with online shopping. Second, the sample was refined using **screening criteria**: participants had to (1) be residents of Doha, (2) have made at least one online purchase in the past three months on the selected platforms, and (3) be aged 18 or older. Age verification was rigorously enforced: online respondents were required to check a mandatory declaration stating, "I confirm I am 18 or older, understand my participation is voluntary, and acknowledge my responses will remain confidential," while physical survey distributors verbally confirmed age eligibility and declined participation if doubt arose (e.g., approaching students in school uniforms or public spaces frequented by minors). Third, surveys were distributed through dual channels: online links were shared via email and social media groups, while physical copies were administered in adult-majority settings (e.g., workplaces, university campuses, and community centers). During data validation, responses underwent multi-stage checks: (1) consistency between the 18+ checkbox and demographic age brackets (e.g., excluding participants who selected "18–25" but later wrote "17" in open-ended fields), (2) retention of participants who skipped income questions only if their ethics-related answers (e.g., detailed critiques of security policies or deceptive marketing) reflected adult reasoning, and (3) removal of rushed or incomplete submissions (e.g., surveys completed in under two minutes). Researchers were trained to identify and exclude duplicate entries (e.g., matching IP addresses for online surveys or repeated handwriting in physical copies). Ethical compliance was prioritized: anonymity was safeguarded by omitting names, and parental consent was waived as minors were systematically excluded. Finally, data was compiled, anonymized, and analyzed using statistical software, ensuring alignment with the study's goals and institutional guidelines.

Data Analysis Procedure

The study utilized a statistical treatment of data. Additionally, the study utilized frequency count, percentage distribution, mean, and t-test for the following: Frequency count and percentage distribution were employed to determine Problem number 1: 'What is the demographic profile of the consumers in terms of age and sex?'. These statistical tools were used to identify the number of respondents belonging in the age and sex groups, and what part of the total each group represents. This helps provide a clear understanding of the distribution of respondents by age and sex, which is essential for interpreting subsequent findings in the study.

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

Where:

\bar{X}_1 and \bar{X}_2 are the sample means of the two groups being compared.

s_1^2 and s_2^2 are the sample variances of the two groups.

n_1 and n_2 are the sample sizes of the two groups.

The mean and standard deviation were used to ascertain Problem number 2, What is the extent of online retailer ethics in terms of *privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value* when grouped according to age and sex? These statistical tools were used to examine consumers' perceptions on various dimensions of online retail stores. This analysis considered factors such as trust in online transactions, experience with online shopping issues, and perceived fairness in service recovery when taken collectively and grouped according to age and sex.

$$t = \frac{m - \mu}{s / \sqrt{n}}$$

Where:

t = t-test

m = mean

mu = theoretical value

s = standard deviation

{n} = variable set size

t-test were employed to determine Problem number 3: 'Is there a significant difference in the extent of online retailers ethics in terms of *privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value* when grouped according to age and sex?'. This statistical tool was used to compare the perceptions of the different demographic groups. It was used to examine whether male and female consumers, as well as younger and older consumers differ significantly in their perceptions on retailing ethics of selected online stores.

Ethical Considerations. As one of the important considerations for the study's successful conduct, meeting ethical standards when doing research was greatly upheld.

Informed consent. Informed consent was obtained from all participants through a clear and upfront disclosure process. For online surveys, the first page presented a standalone consent form requiring respondents to actively check a box indicating: "This is a voluntary research survey aimed at understanding consumer perceptions of retailing ethics in selected online stores in Doha, Qatar. The study examines ethical challenges in online retail, such as privacy breaches and deceptive practices, and aims to identify key concerns that influence consumer trust and purchasing intentions. While participation poses minimal risks, such as potential emotional discomfort when discussing experiences, you have the option to withdraw at any time without penalty. Participants must be 18 years or older, and all responses will be treated confidentially and anonymized, with no personally identifiable information linked to your responses. Your insights could contribute to enhancing ethical practices in online retailing". Participants could not proceed to the survey without this confirmation. For physical copies, the same consent statement was prominently displayed at the top of the first page. Participants signified their agreement by completing the survey, with researchers also providing verbal confirmation of their understanding when distributing the forms.

Vulnerability of the research participants. To ensure clarity and understanding, the consent process was simplified by using plain, non-technical language in both the consent form and survey instructions. For participants using physical copies, a verbal summary of the study's goals and procedures was also provided. Those who had difficulty were given additional explanations, and individuals who remained confused were excluded to protect their rights. Contact information, including an email address, was made available for participants to ask questions at any stage of the study. Throughout the process, it was emphasized that participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents could skip any questions or withdraw at any time without any consequences.

Risks and benefits. The primary risks to participants involved potential concerns regarding their identity and the confidentiality of their responses. To minimize these risks, a clear and concise informed consent statement was included at the beginning of the survey, requiring participants to confirm their understanding of the study's purpose, associated risks, and their right to withdraw at any time. Privacy was safeguarded by not collecting any personal identifiable information, securely storing data in password-protected files accessible only to the research team, and reporting results in summarized form to prevent individual identification. Recognizing possible participant vulnerability, the survey used simplified language to ensure understanding, and an email contact for the researcher was provided for any questions or concerns. Voluntary participation was emphasized throughout, with participants free to skip questions or exit the survey at any time without penalty. The study also outlined potential benefits, such as contributing to the improvement of ethical standards in Qatar's e-commerce sector. Participants were informed that their responses could help online retailers adopt practices that better protect consumer rights and build trust.

Privacy and Confidentiality. To address privacy and confidentiality concerns, the researchers did not require the respondents to indicate their names in the survey questionnaire. In the same manner, other information obtained from the study was disclosed and used for any purpose other than those indicated by the researchers in the letter of informed consent.

Transparency. The researcher prepared letters of permission prior to conducting the pilot test and the main survey. The researcher explained that they had the right to decline or withdraw whenever they felt uncomfortable about their involvement.

Community involvement. The study engaged local consumers in Doha, Qatar, to foster alignment between online retailers and community expectations. By analyzing participant feedback, the research highlighted key ethical strengths, such as robust security measures in payment systems, and areas needing improvement, such as transparency in product descriptions and return policies.

Confidentiality. To uphold ethical standards, this study ensured the anonymity of all respondents. Personal information, such as names and email addresses, were collected but not disclosed. Additionally, the online stores referenced in the survey were not explicitly mentioned in the study to protect the confidentiality of business-related data.

Results

The following tables present an analysis of consumers' perception on retailing ethics of selected online stores. It examines how these perceptions may differ from dissimilar demographics. Tables 1.1 and 1.2 outline the profile of the respondents, providing key details about the sample population taken. This relates to the first research question: 'What is the demographic profile of the consumer in terms of age and sex?'. Tables 2.1 to 2.14 provide an overview of the consumers general view regarding the online retailing ethics in online retailing. This answers the second research question: 'What is the extent of online retailer ethics in terms of *privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value* when grouped according to age and sex?'. Tables 3.1 and 3.2 answers the third research question: 'Is there a significant difference in the extent of online retailers ethics in terms of *privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value* when grouped according to age and sex?'.

1. The demographic profile of the consumers in terms of age and sex

Table 1.1

The Demographic Profile of The Respondents In Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Younger (18-37)	53	45.3
Older (38+)	64	54.7
Total	117	100

Table 1.1 presents the distribution of respondents based on age groups. Out of a total of 117 respondents are 53 individuals, representing 45.3% which are categorized as younger (aged 18-37). Meanwhile, 64 respondents account for 54.7%, which are classified as older (aged 38 and above). This indicates a slightly higher proportion of respondents in the older age group compared to the younger group.

The demographic profile suggests most of the respondents are in the older age bracket (38+), though the difference between the two groups is not substantial. This implies that the product or service appeals broadly across age categories, with a slight leaning toward mature consumers. Understanding this distribution can help tailor marketing strategies that resonate with the predominant age group. Recognizing the preferences of older respondents particularly their concerns about *security*, *privacy*, and *reliability* will allow online retailers to develop more targeted approaches that address the ethical concerns important to this demographic.

According to Alkailani & Abu-Shanab (2021), as older respondents often have higher disposable income, increased job stability, and face time constraints that make online shopping more convenient, they are more likely to engage in e-commerce. Furthermore, older respondents tend to prioritize ethical aspects such as transaction security, privacy, and reliability in e-commerce platforms, which corresponds with the focus of this study on ethical considerations in consumer behavior (Al-Azzawi et al., 2021).

Table 1.2
The Demographic Profile of The Respondents In Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	40	34.2
Female	77	65.8
Total	117	100

Table 1.2 states the demographic profile of respondents based on their sex, showing the distribution of male and female participants. Out of a total of 117 respondents, 40 individuals are male, constituting 34.2% of the sample. Moreover, 77 individuals are female, making up 65.8%. This indicates that females significantly outnumber males in the respondent group.

The data suggests a higher representation of females among the respondents, comprising nearly two-thirds of the sample size. This disparity aligns with studies highlighting gendered participation trends in online retail ethics research. This markup towards female respondents suggests that the study's target population or the context of data collection is more accessible or attractive amongst female participants. This showcases that perspectives amongst female perception could greatly reflect gender-related differences in engagement or availability.

According to Singh et al. (2024), women are more likely to engage in surveys evaluating ethical practices due to heightened concerns about privacy and transparency in e-commerce. Another study found that female consumers dominate research on online shopping behavior because they give importance to factors such as trust and reliability in digital transactions (Suman et al., 2019)

2. The extent of online retailer ethics in terms of *privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value* when grouped according to age and sex

Table 2.1

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Age Based on Dimension: Privacy

Dimension	Younger (18-37)		Older (38+)	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
1. Privacy				
The site clearly explains how user information is used.	3.23	E	3.09	E
Information regarding the privacy policy is clearly presented.	3.21	E	3.09	E
The site shows that it complies with the rules and regulations governing online data protection.	3.08	E	3.13	E
Mean of means	3.17	E	3.10	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.1 States that this dimension compares perceptions of privacy-related aspects between two age groups: Younger (18-37) and Older (38+). For each group, three items are rated on a scale that measure perceived clarity and compliance regarding privacy practices. Using the average mean on the perceived ethics the younger group garnered a mean score that is slightly higher across all items, with a combined mean of 3.17, indicating a generally positive perception. The Older group's means are marginally lower, with a combined mean of 3.10, suggesting a slightly less favorable view albeit still regarding the dimension as ethical.

The higher scores among the Younger group imply they are more confident or satisfied with how the website handles privacy information, possibly due to better understanding or more trust in the site's privacy practices. The differences, though modest, support the idea that age influences perceptions of online privacy transparency. Both groups generally view privacy policies positively; however, the slight decline in scores among the Older group might indicate a need for clearer communication or enhanced transparency tailored to this demographic.

This aligns with previous findings that younger users are more adaptive and trusting of online privacy mechanisms, while older adults show greater concern about data misuse and require more detailed privacy assurances to feel secure in digital transactions (Nalini et al., 2024). Furthermore, older adults are more cautious and less trusting of online platforms' privacy practices due to limited digital literacy, while younger users, more immersed in digital environments, tend to report greater confidence in privacy protections (Jiang et al., 2016).

Table 2.2

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Age Based on Dimension: Security

Dimension	Younger (18-37)		Older (38+)	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
2. Security				
The site appears to offer secured payment methods.	3.43	HE	2.97	E
The security policy is easy to understand.	3.32	HE	2.98	E
The site has adequate security features.	3.25	E	3.03	E
Mean of means	3.33	HE	2.99	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.2 presents data on perceived *security* features related to a website, comparing younger (18-37) and older (38+) age groups. For each group, three items assess the perceptions of security by: offered payment methods, clarity of security policy, and security features using mean scores. The younger group's mean scores are notably higher, with an overall mean of 3.33, indicating a generally positive perception of the site's security. In contrast, the older group's mean scores are lower, with an overall mean of 2.99, indicating ethical standards towards the site's security measures.

The higher *security* perception scores among the younger group suggest they feel more confident in the website's security protocols, possibly due to greater familiarity or trust in digital security measures. Conversely, the Older group's lower yet still ethical scores imply moderate or standard ethical behaviour regarding the security of the site's payment methods and policies. The substantial difference in mean scores (3.33 vs. 2.99) supports the notion that age influences perceptions of online security, with younger users perceiving the site as more secure.

This disparity aligns with Jiang et al. (2016), who found that younger users exhibit greater trust in digital security due to higher familiarity with technology and proactive engagement in protective behaviors. The same study emphasized that younger generations perceive online platforms as inherently secure, driven by frequent exposure to digital transactions. Similar study shows again that support is that Older adults, especially Boomers, were concerned about their privacy so much that some avoid Internet and social media use. Previous research on generational differences on privacy concerns are equivocal (Jiang et al. 2016).

Table 2.3

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Age Based on Dimension: Reliability

Dimension	Younger (18-37)		Older (38+)	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
3. Reliability				
The price shown on the site is the actual amount billed.	3.38	HE	2.97	E
You get what you ordered from this site.	3.21	E	2.89	E
Promises to do something by a certain time, they do it.	3.08	E	2.95	E
The products I looked at were available.	3.09	E	3.00	E
Mean of means	3.19	E	2.95	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE = Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.3 indicates that this dimension assesses perceptions of *reliability* between two age groups: Younger (18-37) and Older (38+). For each group, four items are rated on a scale measuring aspects such as pricing accuracy, fulfillment of orders, timeliness, and product availability.

The mean scores for the Younger group on *reliability* range from 3.08 to 3.38, with an overall mean of 3.19, reflecting generally positive perceptions of the site's reliability. Conversely, the Older group's scores are slightly lower, ranging from 2.89 to 3.00, with a mean of 2.95, indicating a somewhat less favorable view of reliability aspects. The higher reliability scores among the Younger group suggest they are more confident in the site's ability to deliver accurate billing, fulfill orders correctly, meet promised deadlines, and maintain product availability. This may be attributed to greater familiarity with online shopping or higher expectations of service consistency within this demographic. The slightly lower scores in the Older group could reflect more cautious perceptions or experiences of inconsistency, possibly due to less frequent online shopping or different expectations. Overall, while both groups generally perceive the site as reliable, the data imply that age influences perceptions of reliability, with younger users exhibiting greater confidence. These findings highlight the importance of enhancing reliability assurances and transparent communication tailored for older consumers to foster greater trust in online platforms.

This gap aligns with the study of Chopik et al. (2018), who found that younger adults exhibit greater trust in online platforms due to frequent engagement with digital services, fostering familiarity and higher expectations of consistency. Suman et al. (2019) also noted that older adults often encounter barriers such as concerns over product quality and fulfillment reliability in online shopping, which may contribute to their lower trust in e-commerce platforms

Table 2.4

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Age Based on Dimension: Non-Deception

Dimension	Younger (18-37)		Older (38+)	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
4. Non-Deception				
The site exaggerates the benefits and characteristics of its offerings.	2.19	SE	2.16	SE
This site takes advantage of less experienced consumers to make them purchase.	2.57	E	2.16	SE
This site attempts to persuade you to buy things you don't need.	2.13	SE	2.16	SE

This site is not entirely truthful about its offerings.

2.57	E	2.25	SE
Mean of means	2.36	SE	2.18 SE

Note: Reverse scoring was used for the variable "Non-Deception" because of their negative indicators,

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation. 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.4 presents a comparison of perceptions regarding *non-deception* practices on e-commerce websites between younger (18-37) and older (38+) age groups. For each demographic, four items are rated to assess the extent to which websites exaggerate benefits, take advantage of less experienced consumers, persuade unnecessary purchases, and are truthful about their offerings. The mean scores for the younger group hover around 2.13 to 2.57, with an overall mean of 2.36, indicating perceptions that lean toward ethical but with some concern about deception. The older group's mean scores are slightly lower, ranging from 2.16 to 2.25, with an overall mean of 2.18, suggesting a marginally more cautious view of the website's honesty and marketing tactics.

The values presented are the only ones which showcase a low perception in terms of ethics within the age demographic of each dimension. However, the slightly higher mean scores among the younger group imply they perceive the website's deceptive practices more leniently or are more tolerant of the exaggerated claims. Conversely, the older group exhibits marginally more critical perceptions, possibly reflecting greater skepticism or awareness of deceptive marketing practices. The closeness of the scores indicates that both age groups generally view the websites as slightly ethical, though neither perceives them as entirely honest which showcases a level of negativity on its value. These findings suggest that both age brackets are generally skeptical as well as view the dimension as negative due to its deceptive action, which shows that there might be a level of improvement needed regarding its ethics.

A study by Bhattacharya et al. (2021) attributes to younger users' leniency to their familiarity with digital marketing tactics, which may desensitize them to exaggerated claims, fostering a more forgiving stance. In addition, young shoppers are more likely to make online impulse purchases than adult online shoppers, and are more likely influenced by marketing stimuli seen online (Real, 2024). This trend is consistent with recent research by Ghali-Zinoubi (2023), who found that consumer perceptions of online retailers' ethics—particularly around non-deception—vary significantly by age group. The study emphasized that older consumers are more likely to associate persuasive exaggerations with ethical breaches, often due to higher expectations of transparency and less frequent exposure to modern digital marketing tactics.

Table 2.5

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Age Based on Dimension: Service Recovery

Dimension	Younger (18-37)		Older (38+)	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
5. Service Recovery				
This online store has a return policy.	3.26	HE	2.86	E
There is a compensated policy for any delay in delivery of products/services.	2.87	E	2.73	E
This online store has a tracking mechanism for service recovery to identify customer satisfaction.	3.32	HE	2.84	E
This online store tells you what to do when online transaction cannot be completed.	3.19	E	2.83	E
Mean of means	3.16	E	2.82	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.5 presents a comparison of perceptions related to *service recovery* practices in online stores between younger (18-37) and older (38+) age groups. For each demographic, four items are rated to assess the presence of return policies, compensated policies for delays, tracking mechanisms for *service recovery*, and guidance on transaction issues. In the younger group, the mean scores range from 3.19 to 3.32, with an overall mean of 3.16, indicating that respondents generally perceive the service recovery practices as ethical but with room for improvement. In contrast, the older group's mean scores are slightly lower, ranging from 2.73 to 2.86, with an overall mean of 2.82, suggesting a somewhat more cautious or less positive perception of the online store's service recovery measures.

The scores across both age groups reflect perceptions that lean toward ethical standards in service recovery, though the slightly higher means among the younger respondents indicate a more favorable view of the store's recovery policies. Conversely, the older group's lower scores suggest they are somewhat more skeptical of the effectiveness or sufficiency of these practices. Overall, both groups recognize the importance of service recovery practices, though perceptions differ slightly, indicating potential areas for online stores to enhance transparency and effectiveness in addressing customer issues to improve trust across demographics.

A study by Jung & Seock (2017) also attributed this gap to generational differences in expectations. Their findings noted that older respondents prioritize tangible resolutions and human interaction, whereas younger users value digital efficiency and streamlined processes. Alzoubi et al. (2020) further emphasized that effective service recovery directly impacts customer satisfaction and loyalty, particularly when transparency and proactive communication are prioritized.

Table 2.6

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Age Based on Dimension: Shared Value

Dimension	Younger (18-37)		Older (38+)	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
6. Shared Value				
The online service provider respects our service values.	3.25	E	3.00	E
The online service provider and our company have a mutual understanding of each other's business values.	3.17	E	2.92	E
The online service provider sticks to highest level of business ethics in all its transactions.	3.11	E	2.97	E
Mean of means	3.18	E	2.96	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.6 compares perceptions of *shared value* between younger (18-37) and older (38+) age groups regarding their online service providers. For each age group, three items assess the extent to which the provider respects service values, understands mutual business values, and adheres to high ethical standards in transactions. The younger group's mean scores are 3.25, 3.17, and 3.11 respectively, with an overall mean of 3.18, indicating an ethical perception of the service provider's shared values. The older group's mean scores are slightly lower at 3.00, 2.92, and 2.97, with an overall mean of 2.96, which still falls within the ethical range but suggests a marginally less positive perception among older consumers.

The data shows that both age groups generally perceive the online service provider as ethically aligned with shared values, though the younger group perceives these values more favorably. The slight decrease in mean scores among the older group may reflect a more cautious or critical view of the provider's commitment to shared service and business ethics. The differences suggest varying levels of trust or expectations regarding ethical practices across age demographics. Overall, both groups view the provider's shared value practices as ethical, but there is a small perception gap that might benefit from improved communication or reinforcement of shared values to bolster trust among older consumers. These findings highlight the importance of maintaining high ethical standards to satisfy diverse consumer perceptions across age groups.

According to Zolotoy et al. (2020), it was noted that younger consumers are more likely to trust businesses that align with social causes, while older adults prioritize long-term consistency in ethical perceptions. Additionally, older consumers' critical views stem from experiences with unethical marketing, leading them to scrutinize shared value claims more rigorously (Calabrese et al., 2016).

Table 2.7**Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Age**

Dimensions	Younger (n=53)		Older(n=64)	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
1. Privacy				
The site clearly explains how user information is used.	3.23	E	3.09	E
Information regarding the privacy policy is clearly presented.	3.21	E	3.09	E
The site shows that it complies with the rules and regulations governing online data protection.	3.08	E	3.13	E
Mean of means	3.17	E	3.10	E
2. Security				
The site appears to offer secured payment methods.	3.43	HE	2.97	E
The security policy is easy to understand.	3.32	HE	2.98	E
The site has adequate security features.	3.25	E	3.03	E
Mean of means	3.33	HE	2.99	E
3. Reliability				
The price shown on the site is the actual amount billed.	3.38	HE	2.97	E
You get what you ordered from this site.	3.21	E	2.89	E
Promises to do something by a certain time, they do it.	3.08	E	2.95	E
The products I looked at were available.	3.09	E	3.00	E
Mean of means	3.19	E	2.95	E
4. Non- Deception				
The site exaggerates the benefits and characteristics of its offerings.	2.19	SE	2.16	SE
This site takes advantage of less experienced consumers to make them purchase.	2.57	E	2.16	SE
This site attempts to persuade you to buy things that you do need.	2.13	SE	2.16	SE

This site is not entirely truthful about its offerings.	2.57	E	2.2	SE
Mean of means	2.36	SE	2.1	SE
5. Service Recovery				
This online store has a return policy.	3.26	HE	2.8	E
There is a compensated policy for any delay in delivery of products/services.	2.87	E	2.7	E
This online store has a tracking mechanism for service recovery to identify customer satisfaction.	3.32	HE	2.8	E
This online store tells you what to do when online transaction cannot be completed.	3.19	E	2.8	E
Mean of means	3.16	E	2.8	E
6. Shared Value				
The online service provider respects our service values.	3.25	E	3.0	E
The online service provider and our company have a mutual understanding of each other's business values.	3.17	E	2.9	E
The online service provider sticks to highest level of business ethics in all its transactions.	3.11	E	2.9	E
Mean of means	3.18	E	2.9	E
Overall	3.07	E	2.8	E

Note: Reverse scoring was used for the variable "Non-Deception" because of their negative indicators, \bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation. 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE = Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.7 results represent Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Grouped According to Age. Among younger consumers, the highest mean score was recorded in the *Security* dimension with a mean of 3.33, (SD = 0.574). While the lowest mean score was observed in the *Non-Deception* dimension with a mean of 2.36, (SD = 0.779). In contrast, among older consumers, the highest mean was found in the *Privacy* dimension with a mean of 3.10, (SD = 0.517). And the lowest value of mean was also identified in the *Non-Deception* dimension with a mean of 2.18, (SD= 0.660).

These findings suggest that younger consumers perceive online stores as more secure, indicating higher confidence in secured payment methods, security policies, and site protection features. In contrast, older consumers rated privacy the highest, implying they find online stores more transparent in explaining data use and complying with online data protection policies. However, both age groups rated *Non-deception* the lowest, suggesting skepticism about the honesty of online stores. The relatively low ratings in this category indicate concerns about exaggerated product descriptions, misleading marketing tactics, and perceived manipulation of inexperienced consumers.

According to Schomakers et al. (2017), older users' evaluation of private information differs from those of the younger generations as they are more concerned in dealing with the internet and privacy protection due to their lack of experience and trust. On the other hand, previous research by Jiang et al. (2016) stated that online safety and security is mainly suited and focused on by the general populations such as young

adolescent and college students. Additionally, Non-deception, by the study of Morsink (2024) showed that price transparency was the strongest predictor followed by process transparency and inventory transparency.

The findings indicate notable differences in how younger and older consumers perceive online retailing ethics. Younger consumers demonstrate greater confidence in security measures, while older consumers prioritize privacy and data protection. Despite these differences, both age groups express concerns regarding deception, highlighting skepticism about misleading advertisements and exaggerated product claims. These insights emphasize the need for online retailers to enhance transparency and ethical marketing practices to build consumer trust across all age groups.

Table 2.8

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Sex Based on Dimension: Privacy

Dimension	Male		Female	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
1. Privacy				
The site clearly explains how user information is used;	3.13	E	3.17	E
Information regarding the privacy policy is clearly presented	3.08	E	3.18	E
The site shows that it complies with the rules and regulations governing online data protection.	2.93	E	3.19	E
Mean of means	3.04	E	3.18	E
\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)				

Table 2.8 presents the perceptions of male and female users regarding privacy practices on a website. For males, three items assess the clarity of privacy information, compliance with data protection regulations, and the transparency of privacy policies. The mean scores for males range from 2.93 to 3.13, with an overall mean of 3.04, indicating that male users generally perceive the website's privacy practices as ethically acceptable but with room for improvement. For females, similar items are rated, with mean scores slightly higher, ranging from 3.17 to 3.19, and an overall mean of 3.18. This suggests that female users perceive the privacy practices to be marginally more ethical compared to their male counterparts.

The data reveal that both male and female users view the website's privacy practices positively, aligning with the 'Ethical' category. However, females tend to perceive the site's privacy measures slightly more favorably, which may reflect higher trust or greater concern for privacy among female users. Overall, the findings suggest that the website's privacy policies are perceived as ethically acceptable by users, but ongoing efforts to enhance transparency and compliance could further improve user trust.

Martin and Murphy (2017) found that men often exhibit lower sensitivity to privacy risks in digital environments due to greater confidence in their ability to manage data security, aligning with their relatively neutral perceptions. The close proximity of the mean scores indicates a generally consistent perception across genders, with a slight tendency for females to view privacy compliance more favorably. Liébana-Cabanillas et al. (2018) emphasized that maintaining consistent transparency and proactive privacy updates can further narrow perceptual gaps and enhance trust across demographics.

Table 2.9

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Sex Based on Dimension: Privacy

Dimension	Male		Female	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
2. Security				
The site appears to offer secure payment methods	3.18	E	3.18	E
The security policy is easy to understand	3.10	E	3.16	E
This site has adequate security features.	3.13	E	3.13	E
Mean of means	3.13	E	3.16	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.9 displays the perceptions of male and female respondents regarding the security features of an e-commerce website. For each sex group, three items are evaluated: whether the site offers secure payment methods, if the security policy is easy to understand, and if the site has adequate security features. The mean scores for males are 3.18, 3.10, and 3.13 respectively, resulting in an overall mean of 3.13, while females report mean scores of 3.18, 3.16, and 3.13, with a mean of 3.16. All scores are interpreted as 'E' (Ethical), indicating generally positive perceptions of the security measures on the site across both genders.

The data indicates that both male and female respondents perceive the website's security features favorably, with mean scores slightly above 3.10 on a scale where higher values suggest stronger perceptions of security. The marginal difference between males and females (overall means of 3.13 and 3.16, respectively) suggests that perceptions regarding website security are relatively uniform across genders. Since all scores fall within the 'Ethical' range (3.36 - 4.00), respondents generally view the site as sufficiently secure, trustworthy, and transparent about its security policies. This positive outlook indicates that the website's security features are effective in instilling confidence among users, regardless of gender. However, the close scores also imply that there is little perceived difference in security perceptions based on gender, emphasizing the importance of maintaining consistent security standards to uphold user trust across all demographics.

Venkatesh et al. (2016) suggest that such uniformity may stem from widespread adoption of standardized security protocols (e.g., Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) encryption) in e-commerce, which fosters baseline trust across demographics regardless of gender. Furthermore, Shiao et al. (2019) suggests that modern e-commerce platforms prioritize user-centric security design, minimizing gender disparities by addressing universal concerns like data breaches.

Table 2.10

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Sex Based on Dimension: Reliability

Dimension	Male		Female	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
3. Reliability				
The price shown on the site is the actual amount billed	3.23	E	3.12	E
You get what you ordered from this site	3.05	E	3.03	E
Promises to do something by a certain time, they do it	2.93	E	3.05	E

The products I looked at were available.	2.95	E	3.09	E
Mean of means	3.04	E	3.07	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.10 Reliability ratings for male and female respondents across various dimensions. For males, the mean scores across the four items range from 2.93 to 3.23, with an overall mean of 3.04. This suggests a generally positive perception of reliability, with respondents mostly agreeing that the site's prices are accurate, they receive what they ordered, promises are kept, and products are available. For females, the mean scores are slightly lower, ranging from 3.03 to 3.12, with an overall mean of 3.07, indicating similarly positive perceptions but with a marginally more cautious view. Both genders rate reliability as ethically acceptable, with scores falling within the "Ethical" to "Highly Ethical" range, suggesting that users generally trust the website's reliability practices.

The values indicate that both male and female respondents perceive the website's reliability practices positively, with mean scores close to 3.0, which falls within the "Ethical" range. Males tend to rate reliability slightly higher than females, implying a marginally higher level of trust or satisfaction regarding the website's reliability. The close proximity of the scores suggests that gender does not significantly influence perceptions of reliability, and both groups regard the website as generally trustworthy and dependable. These perceptions reflect a favorable view of the website's honesty in pricing, fulfillment, and product availability, though continuous improvements could further enhance trustworthiness across both demographics.

These findings align with prior research, which has shown that while both men and women report favorable trust attitudes toward e-commerce sites, men often exhibit marginally higher trust levels, particularly in contexts involving reliability and ethical behavior (Sohaib et al., 2018). A study by Pradhana & Sastiono (2019) suggests that men tend to spend more than women in total when shopping online, with the level of trust being the most significant factor influencing how often they shop and how much they spend. In the same study, it is noted that while men's risk aversion affects their online shopping behavior, women's risk aversion does not show a significant impact.

Table 2.11
Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Grouped According to Sex Based on Dimension: Non-Deception

Dimension	Male		Female	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
4. Non-Deception				
The site exaggerates the benefits and characteristics of its offerings	2.00	SE	2.26	SE
This site takes advantage of less experienced consumers to make them purchase;	2.33	SE	2.35	SE
This site attempts to persuade you to buy things that you do not need	2.13	SE	2.16	SE
This site is not entirely truthful about its offerings	2.38	SE	2.40	SE
Mean of means	2.21	SE	2.99	SE

Note: Reverse scoring was used for the variable "Non-Deception" because of their negative indicators, \bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation. 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.11 displays the perceptions of *non-deception* practices on e-commerce websites by gender, focusing on four key items: exaggeration of benefits, taking advantage of less experienced consumers, persuading unnecessary purchases, and overall truthfulness about offerings. For males, the mean scores range

from 2.13 to 2.38, with an overall mean of 2.21, indicating a perception that these websites are somewhat deceptive but not highly unethical.

Females, on the other hand, report slightly higher mean scores, ranging from 2.16 to 2.40, with an overall mean of 2.99, suggesting a marginally more skeptical view of the honesty and marketing tactics employed by these sites. Results further showed in another study that females prefer to shop online in a robust legal framework. The data reveal that both genders perceive e-commerce sites as somewhat deceptive, with females tending to view these practices as slightly more unethical than males. The mean scores for both groups fall within the "Slightly Ethical" to "Ethically Neutral" range, indicating a general awareness or suspicion of deceptive tactics, though not to an extreme degree. The higher overall mean among females suggests they may be more cautious or critical regarding the honesty of online offerings. These findings highlight that perceptions of non-deception are relatively consistent across genders, with a slight tendency for females to perceive higher levels of deception. This insight underscores the importance for e-commerce platforms to enhance transparency and build trust among consumers of all genders.

A similar study showed that male internet users perceive a lower risk associated with online shopping than female internet users (Lim et al., 2019). Furthermore, they desire to shop in a safe environment, fenced by rules and regulations, assured that they can report and complain to the concerned legal authorities if there is a mishap occurring during their online shopping tenure (Akhlaq & Ahmed, 2016).

Table 2.12
Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Sex Based on Dimension: Service Recovery

Dimension	Male		Female	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
5. Service Recovery				
This online store has a return policy	3.00	E	3.06	E
There is a compensated policy for any delay in delivery of products/services;	3.73	E	2.83	E
This online store has a tracking mechanism for service recovery to identify customer satisfaction;	3.05	E	3.06	E
This online store tells you what to do when online transaction cannot be completed.	2.98	E	3.00	E
Mean of means	2.94	E	2.99	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE = Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.12 compares male and female consumers' perceptions of service recovery ethics in online retailing across four dimensions: return policy, compensated delay policy, tracking mechanism, and guidance for failed transactions. All items were rated within the "Ethical" (2.51–3.25) range, though gender-based differences emerged. For return policies, both genders rated them as ethical, with females slightly more favorable (3.06 vs. 3.00), suggesting that women may place higher value on structured return processes.

A significant disparity appeared in the compensated delay policy, where males rated it much higher (3.73) than females (2.83), indicating that men may view compensations like refunds or vouchers as sufficient, while women may find them inadequate or inconsistently applied—reflecting a possible difference in expectations. Tracking mechanisms received nearly identical scores (3.05 for males, 3.06 for females), suggesting both genders equally value transparency and real-time updates. Similarly, guidance for failed transactions was rated closely (2.98 for males, 3.00 for females), implying both groups see room for improvement in support during transactional issues. The overall perception, based on the average of all dimensions, shows females slightly more favorable (2.99) compared to males (2.94), possibly due to their

higher scores in return policies and guidance. Key takeaways highlight the need to improve compensated delay policies.

This aligns with findings by Abdulla et al. (2021), who emphasized that consumers' perceived value of return policy leniency—such as effort, time, and clarity—can influence purchase behavior, with structured return processes potentially having greater appeal to consumers who are more sensitive to service quality considerations, including many female shoppers. A related study shows by Elsayy & Fayyad, (2018) that males focus on tangible outcomes to handle service failure especially for women, while tracking and return processes appear to meet shared standards. Retailers should consider targeted communication strategies, emphasizing fairness and clarity for female consumers and efficiency for males. Standardizing compensation policies and investing in user-friendly tools can enhance trust and satisfaction across genders.

Table 2.13

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Sex Based on Dimension: Shared Value

Dimension	Male		Female	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
6. Shared Values				
The online service provider respects our business values;	3.18	E	3.08	E
The online service provider and our company have a mutual understanding of each other's business values;	3.08	E	3.01	E
The online service provider sticks to the highest level of business ethics in all its transactions.	3.03	E	3.04	E
Mean of means	3.09	E	3.04	E

\bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation: 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE = Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.13 displays the perceptions of male and female respondents regarding the *shared values* dimension of the online service provider. For both genders, three items are assessed: whether the provider respects the company's business values, whether there is mutual understanding of business values, and whether the provider adheres to high standards of business ethics. The mean scores for males are consistently at 3.18, 3.08, and 3.03 respectively, with an overall mean of 3.09, indicating that males generally perceive the provider's shared values as ethical. Females obtained different mean scores of 3.08, 3.01, and 3.04 for the respective items, resulting in an overall mean of 3.04.

The mean scores across male and female respondents highlight a consensus in perceptions regarding the provider's commitment to shared values and ethical conduct. The mean scores of 3.04 and 3.09 indicate that both groups view the provider as reasonably ethical in its dealings, with the exceptions that men scored higher with respect for business values and mutual understanding being perceived positively. This consistency suggests that gender does not significantly influence perceptions of shared values in this context. Overall, respondents perceive the online service provider's commitment to ethical business practices favorably, reflecting confidence in the provider's adherence to shared business morals. The findings imply that the provider's efforts to uphold shared values are effective across gender groups, contributing to a trustworthy reputation.

According to (Dion, 2021), the perceived perspective on shared values by the provider is reasonably ethical in its dealings, with respect for business values and mutual understanding being viewed positively. Other findings show that happiness, love and satisfaction have significant influence on online consumer purchase behaviour, while fashion consciousness moderates the relationship between consumer values and online purchase behaviour (Adeola et al., 2021)

Table 2.14

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Group According to Sex

Dimensions	Male		Female	
	\bar{x}	VI	\bar{x}	VI
1. Privacy				
The site clearly explains how user information is used.	3.13	E	3.17	E
Information regarding the privacy policy is clearly presented.	3.08	E	3.18	E
The site shows that it complies with the rules and regulations governing online data protection.	2.93	E	3.19	E
Mean of means	3.04	E	3.18	E
2. Security				
The site appears to offer secure payment methods.	3.18	E	3.18	E
The security policy is easy to understand.	3.10	E	3.16	E
The site has adequate security features.	3.13	E	3.13	E
Mean of means	3.13	E	3.16	E
3. Reliability				
The price shown on the site is the actual amount billed.	3.23	E	3.12	E
You get what you ordered from this site.	3.05	E	3.03	E
Promises to do something by a certain time, they do it.	2.93	E	3.05	E
The products I looked at were available.	2.95	E	3.09	E
Mean of means	3.04	E	3.07	E
4. Non-Deception				
The site exaggerates the benefits and characteristics of its offerings.	2.00	SE	2.26	SE
This site takes advantage of less experienced consumers to make them purchase.	2.33	SE	2.35	SE
This site attempts to persuade you to buy things that you do not need.	2.13	SE	2.16	SE
This site is not entirely truthful about its offerings.	2.38	SE	2.40	SE
Mean of means	2.21	SE	2.29	SE
5. Service Recovery				
This online store has a return policy.	3.00	E	3.06	E
There is a compensated policy for any delay in delivery of products/services.	2.73	E	2.83	E
This online store has a tracking mechanism for service recovery to identify customer satisfaction.	3.05	E	3.06	E
This online store tells you what to do when online transactions cannot be completed.	2.98	E	3.00	E
Mean of means	2.94	E	2.99	E
6. Shared Value				
The online service provider respects our business values.	3.18	E	3.08	E
The online service provider and our company have a mutual understanding of each other's business values.	3.08	E	3.01	E

The online service provider sticks to highest level of business ethics in all its transactions.	3.03	E	3.04	E
Mean of means	3.09	E	3.04	E
Overall	2.90	E	2.95	E

Note: Reverse scoring was used for the variable "Non-Deception" because of their negative indicators, \bar{x} = mean, VI = verbal interpretation. 3.36 - 4.00 (HE = highly ethical), 2.51 - 3.25 (E = Ethical) 1.76 - 2.50 (SE= Slightly Ethical), 1.00 - 1.75 (NE = Not Ethical)

Table 2.14 showed Security as the highest scoring dimension for the male sex group with a mean of 3.13. Meanwhile, the dimension with the lowest score is Non-Deception with a mean of means of 2.21. In contrast, the highest scoring dimension for the female population is Privacy, with a mean of means of 3.18. Similar to the male population of respondents, Non-Deception is also the lowest scoring dimension with a mean of means of (2.29).

Results show the differences in perceived ethics of online retailing between male and female respondents. For males, the highest scoring dimension is Security, indicating a strong emphasis on feeling secure in their interactions or experiences, while the lower score in Non-Deception suggests concerns over honesty and transparency. Conversely, the female population places the highest value on Privacy, reflecting a heightened awareness and concern for personal information and its protection. The slightly lower score in Non-Deception for females relates to the male respondents which also suggests that, while they value honesty, their emphasis on privacy may lead to a perception that non-deceptive practices are not sufficiently prioritized or valued.

According to Albert et al. (2019), this means that males appear to be more comfortable engaging in mobile banking, less concerned about privacy on social media sites, and more likely to encounter malware, potentially due to their riskier browsing habits, than are females. On the other hand, Fox et al. (2022) suggested that privacy labels play a significant role in shaping consumer perceptions, particularly by boosting the willingness to share data and engage in transactions with online organizations. When clear privacy controls are offered, they help to build trust among consumers (Aïmeur et al., 2016). In essence, transparency into data practices would breed this very much-needed trust; consumers prefer those brands which clearly spell out how their data will be used. (Singh et al., 2024) found that generally, women are more concerned about privacy and the dissemination of personal information online compared to men. Non-deception, by a recent study from Morsink (2024), showed that price transparency was the strongest predictor followed by process transparency and inventory transparency.

3. The significant difference in the extent of online retailers ethics in terms of *privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value when grouped according to age and sex*

Table 3.1

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Grouped According to Age

Dimensions	Computed t	P-value	Sig. @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Privacy	0.638	0.524	Not Significant	Accepted
Security	3.206	0.001	Significant	Not Accepted
Reliability	2.141	0.034	Significant	Not Accepted
Non-Deception	1.358	0.177	Not Significant	Accepted
Service Recovery	3.322	0.001	Significant	Not Accepted
Shared Values	1.831	0.069	Not Significant	Accepted

Note: The values were computed using t-test on their given p-value, indicators of 0.00 to 0.05 as significant and indicators of 0.09 and onwards are not significant.

Table 3.1 The data presented showcases the significant difference when grouped according to consumers' perceptions of online retailing ethics when grouped according to age. The findings reveal that age significantly influences perceptions of *Security*, *Reliability*, and *Service Recovery*. For *Security* ($p = 0.001$), younger and older consumers differ in how they evaluate the safety measures implemented by online stores, such as data protection and secure transactions. For *Reliability* ($p = 0.034$), perceptions of the dependability and trustworthiness of online retailers vary across age groups. *Service Recovery* ($p = 0.001$) also shows a significant difference, indicating that age affects how consumers perceive the way online stores handle complaints and resolve issues. In contrast, *Privacy* ($p = 0.524$), *Non-Deception* ($p = 0.177$), and *Shared Value* ($p = 0.069$) do not show significant differences among age groups. This suggests that consumers, regardless of age, share similar views on how online retailers protect their personal information, their honesty and transparency, and the ethical principles they uphold. Although Shared Values approaches significance, it remains consistent across different age groups.

Older consumers tend to be more suspicious about online security. They often have less confidence in their abilities to protect themselves online, are uncertain about the effectiveness of protection resources, perform fewer protective behaviors, and are more likely to rely on others for assistance compared to younger consumers (Jiang et al., 2016). Moreover, Customers' age influences how they perceive the seriousness of service failures and their expectations for service recovery. Additionally, older adults tend to show greater emotional resilience in social conflicts, experiencing fewer negative reactions compared to younger individuals (Charles & Luong 2019). As people grow older, they often develop a deeper understanding and greater patience, which helps them handle conflicts more efficiently. Consequently, they become more skilled at managing interpersonal difficulties. (Beitler et al., 2018). Lastly, younger consumers typically balance work and family, which leads to a mixed shopping approach. However, older consumers, especially those in the later stages of this generation, often show more caution when shopping online. While consumers value the convenience of online shopping, many still prefer the reliability of traditional stores due to concerns over product quality and trustworthiness (Fromm & Read, 2018).

According to Ismail and Wahid (2022), Performance expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions are factors that affect older adults' perceptions. Conversely, the main barriers that they face include concerns about usage, value, risk, and adherence to traditional shopping methods. Compared to older adult consumers of online shopping, younger respondents have considerably higher drivers and lower barriers to purchase online. When compared to young consumers of online shopping, older adults encounter more obstacles in online shopping (Suman et al., 2019).

Table 3.2

Consumers' Perception on Retailing Ethics of Online Stores When Grouped According to Sex

Dimensions	Computed t	P-value	Sig. @ 0.05	Status of Hypothesis
Privacy	1.368	0.174	Not Significant	Accepted
Security	0.210	0.833	Not Significant	Accepted
Reliability	0.305	0.760	Not Significant	Accepted
Non-Deception	0.670	0.504	Not Significant	Accepted
Service Recovery	0.459	0.646	Not Significant	Accepted

Shared Values	-0.435	0.663	Not Significant	Accepted
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Note: The values were computed using t-test on their given p-value, indicators of 0.00 to 0.05 as significant and indicators of 0.09 and onwards are not significant.

Table 3.2 shows the hypothesis testing on consumers' perceptions of online retailing ethics when grouped according to sex, focusing on six dimensions: *Privacy*, *Security*, *Reliability*, *Non-Deception*, *Service Recovery*, and *Shared Values*. Across all dimensions, the computed p-values were more notable than the significance level of 0.05, indicating no significant differences in perceptions between male and female consumers.

This suggests that sex does not play a crucial role in shaping consumers' ethical concerns when engaging in online shopping. The results reinforce the idea that perceptions of digital retail ethics are influenced more by individual experiences and expectations rather than by one's sex. For *Privacy*, both sexes conveyed similarities in their perceptions of how online stores handle personal information. Regarding *Security*, there was no notable difference in how both sexes perceive the safety measures of online stores. *Reliability* and *Non-Deception* also showed no significant variations, suggesting that both genders equally trust the dependability of online retailers and believe they act truthfully. *Service Recovery* and *Shared Values* were also perceived consistently across both sexes, implying that they align their views on how online stores address complaints and reflect shared ethical principles.

Another study indicates that there are no significant differences in perception gender wise in ethical issues for virtual shopping in privacy and security (Rroy & Nayak, 2022).

Discussion

This study reveals that respondents in Doha, Qatar, generally perceive online stores as ethical, particularly in terms of *security and privacy*. The first research question addressed the demographic profile of respondents in terms of age and sex. The data revealed a relatively balanced age distribution, with 45.3% categorized as younger (18-37 years) and 54.7% as older (38 years and above). Notably, the sample was predominantly female (65.8%), which may reflect the higher participation rate of women in online shopping activities or sampling biases. These demographic characteristics set the context for interpreting perceptions of online retail ethics, as age and gender can influence trust, expectations, and ethical concerns in e-commerce.

The second research question examined the overall perception of online retail ethics across six dimensions: *privacy*, *security*, *reliability*, *non-deception*, *service recovery*, and *shared value* when grouped according to age and sex. When according to age: The findings showed that younger consumers (mean = 3.07) generally perceived online stores as more ethical compared to older consumers (mean = 2.84). Significantly, the dimensions of *Security*, *Reliability*, and *Service Recovery* differed notably between age groups. Specifically, younger respondents rated *security* ($p = 0.001$), *reliability* ($p = 0.034$), and *service recovery* ($p = 0.001$) higher than older respondents. This indicates that younger consumers have greater confidence in the safety, dependability, and problem-resolution aspects of online retailers. Conversely, older consumers prioritized *privacy* more than younger ones, reflecting heightened concerns about data protection and transparency.

When comparing perceptions across sex, no significant differences emerged in any of the six dimensions. Both males and females perceived online retailing ethics similarly, with comparable mean scores and p-values exceeding the 0.05 threshold. This suggests that gender does not significantly influence ethical perceptions in online shopping within this sample, aligning with previous research indicating that perceptions of digital ethics tend to be more influenced by individual experiences rather than gender differences.

The third research question focused on whether significant differences exist in perceptions of online retail ethics based on age and sex. The analysis revealed significant differences related to age in *Security*, *Reliability*, and *Service Recovery* (p-values of 0.001, 0.034, and 0.001 respectively). Younger consumers demonstrated higher confidence in the security features and dependability of online stores, whereas older consumers exhibited more skepticism, especially regarding security and reliability. These differences could be attributed to varying levels of technological familiarity, trust, and exposure to online risks across age groups. Interestingly, perceptions of *Privacy*, *Non-Deception*, and *Shared Value* did not significantly differ

between age groups, indicating a shared baseline concern about honesty and ethical principles regardless of age.

Analysis showed no significant differences in perceptions based on sex across all dimensions. Both male and female respondents perceived online retailing ethics, similarly, implying that gender does not play a pivotal role in shaping ethical perceptions in this context. This finding suggests that ethical concerns and expectations are more uniformly distributed across genders among consumers in Doha.

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight key differences in consumer perceptions of online retailing ethics based on age and gender. Older consumers placed a greater emphasis on privacy, expressing heightened concerns over the security of their personal information and data protection. Meanwhile, younger consumers demonstrated greater confidence in online transactions, prioritizing *security*, *reliability*, and *service recovery*, suggesting a higher level of digital adaptability. In contrast, older consumers may exhibit greater caution not only due to lower digital exposure but also because they tend to have more financial savings and assets at risk. This financial responsibility makes them more vigilant about potential online threats, especially those related to fraud and data misuse.

Gender-based differences also emerged, with female consumers placing more importance on *privacy*, reflecting their focus on personal protection in online shopping. Male consumers, on the other hand, prioritized security, focusing on transactional safety and fraud prevention. Despite these variations, both groups shared similar overall perceptions of ethical business practices, acknowledging responsible retailing while remaining cautious about deceptive marketing tactics.

This study suggests that the selected online stores need to reinforce ethical standards, particularly in addressing deceptive practices as it is shown to be the biggest concern when it comes to ethical perception. Reinforcing these standards means more than just compliance—it involves taking proactive steps to ensure transparency in product descriptions, fair pricing, accurate advertising, and honest customer interactions. Retailers should prioritize implementing clear return policies, disclosing all relevant product information, and avoiding misleading visuals or exaggerated claims. By strengthening these ethical practices, retailers can not only reduce consumer skepticism but also build long-term trust and brand loyalty, especially in competitive and rapidly evolving digital markets. This study shows that consumers put their trust in online stores highly in terms of security and privacy, but with some varying degree of skepticism remains regarding product transparency, honesty, and deception as a whole. Which is the biggest factor that should be improved upon. The dimensions in this research show that all perception is generally consistent, albeit varying when it comes to the age gap of our participants, which is shown to have significant differences in their viewpoints and perceptions.

One of the most prominent problems was deceptive marketing as it damages trust and affects buying decisions. To solve this, strengthening issue resolution and clarifying policies will boost trust and loyalty among consumers and help online retailers adapt to evolving expectations and enhance their ethical standards in the e-commerce landscape. For instance, this research can implement and showcase data to online retailers, which they can adopt in a series of guidelines and practices for implementing clear labeling for products that can help consumers make informed decisions. This data can help retailers consider possible options such as creating a dedicated “Customer Trust” section on their websites, that can outline their commitment to ethical practices. To further support our research on what consumers look for in online retail ethics, a website was made that outlines the six key dimensions: privacy, security, reliability, non-deception, service recovery, and shared value. The website explains the importance of each dimension and how they impact consumer trust and behavior illustrating how these ethical principles can be effectively applied in our own business practices to ensure transparency, build consumer loyalty, and promote responsible online shopping environment.

These findings underscore the need for online retailers to enhance transparency, reinforce security protocols, and uphold ethical standards to foster greater consumer trust. This can be achieved through several concrete strategies: providing accurate and detailed product descriptions, ensuring that all pricing and promotional offers are clearly explained without hidden conditions, and openly communicating return and refund policies. Reinforcing security protocols involves safeguarding customer data with strong encryption, offering secure payment gateways, and being transparent about how personal information is collected and used. Upholding ethical standards also means eliminating manipulative marketing tactics, such as fake scarcity or misleading product images, and ensuring fair treatment of customers throughout their shopping

experience. By taking these steps, online retailers can create a more trustworthy and consumer-friendly environment that responds to the ethical concerns highlighted in this study.

Based on the findings, online retailers in Doha can build consumer trust by focusing on simple, actionable improvements. First, ensure clear product descriptions by avoiding exaggerated claims and including honest details like accurate photos, sizes, and verified customer reviews. Second, create a short, easy-to-read FAQ (Frequently Asked Question) page that explains return policies, delivery times, and how customer data is protected, and highlight this information during checkout. Third, offer 24/7 chat support to resolve issues quickly for example, apologizing for delays and offering instant solutions like replacements or discounts. These steps require minimal cost but address key consumer concerns, helping businesses align with local values and foster lasting trust. To further ensure the information is given and utilized to their fullest, the given website mentioned created from this study has created an outline of the important information that could further improve upon retailers as well as it's customer; furthermore, the created website can showcases the importance of this research's concerns of ethical policies as well as its strengths that retailers and customers can use to further inform themselves on the aspects of retailing ethics. Overall, the given recommendations of the findings of this research is on the emphasis on transparency, due to the perceived ethical misguidance of which could be improved upon based on our results and data, thereby fostering greater trust and accountability in the involved stakeholders.

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